

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE FAMILY HOPE PROGRAM THROUGH FAMILY DEVELOPMENT SESSIONS

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to analyse the effectiveness of the Family Hope Program through the Family Development Session (FDS). This study discusses the effectiveness of the program, analyzing the accuracy of program targets, program socialization, program objectives and program monitoring. This study uses a qualitative descriptive method with data collection interviews, observations and documentation. This research was conducted in Sukagalih Village, Tarogong Kidul District, Garut Regency. The research informants were the village head, the head of the welfare section, assistants and representatives of FDS participants. Based on the results of the study indicate that the application of FDS has not been effective. This can be seen from the lack of understanding of the Beneficiary Families (KPM) regarding the material from the modules presented, the lack of KPM participation in FDS time, and passive monitoring so that the achievement of goals has not been maximized. Therefore, several things were recommended, such as the need for assistants to improve their educational capabilities, the need to increase KPM awareness about the importance of participation in FDS, and the need for regular monitoring by village officials in the implementation of FDS. So that KPM that is already socio-economically feasible can be graduated.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Family Development Session, Family Hope Program

1. INTRODUCTION

Poverty can be defined as a low level of income (Kompasiana, 2020). Poverty can also be interpreted as the condition of an individual or a number of people whose acquisition is not sufficient for the basic needs of life. The problem of poverty is triggered by economic factors and gives rise to other broader issues (Dari et al., 2022) such as unemployment, hunger, social inequality, health and welfare in the community. Poverty occurs in various developing countries including Indonesia (Adawiyah, 2020) which can be categorized as a major problem. Poverty is difficult to eliminate but is expected to be controlled and minimized (Rosana, 2019) with appropriate efforts. The government in overcoming the problem of poverty has made various policies and strategies for economic growth. Among them with the issuance of Presidential Regulation No. 15 of 2010, concerning the acceleration of Poverty Reduction which is a refinement of Presidential Regulation No. 13 of 2009 concerning the coordination of Poverty Reduction. One of the poverty control strategies is the Family Hope Program which is a conditional cash assistance strategy given to underprivileged families. The Family Hope Program is one of the family-based integrated social assistance programs (Cluster I). (Kementerian Komunikasi dan Informatika, 2011). The PKH objectives as stated in the PKH

Implementation Guidelines issued by the Ministry of Social Affairs have 5 points, one of which is reducing poverty and inequality.

Furthermore, regarding the Family Development Session, it is stated in the Regulation of the Minister of Social Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 of 2018 concerning the Family Hope Program, in article 32 regarding the mechanism for implementing PKH. The Family Development Session which is one of the stages of PKH helps achieve the five components of the MDG's goals (Millennium Development Goals) that will be assisted by PKH, namely, reducing the underprivileged and undernourished, primary schooling, gender equality, reducing the increase in infant mortality and underage children. 5 years and reduce postpartum maternal mortality (Pratama & Mudarya, 2021). FDS can also be carried out as an effort to break the chain of poverty in Indonesia (Arfiyani et al., 2020).

The PKH KPM assistant acts as a facilitator to facilitate the achievement of PKH goals, namely being able to change mindsets and behavior related to the use of education, health, and social welfare assistance. The implementation of the Very Poor Household Facilitator (RTSM) does not only focus on individual problems or those who need access to services but also social assistance for KPM PKH group meetings that can be carried out in Family Development Sessions (FDS). Family Development Session (FDS) activities are learning activities for several materials for the independence of beneficiary families such as managing family finances, parenting children, becoming better parents, starting a business, and other materials. (Kementerian Sosial, 2021).

The PKH KPM group meeting is a routine activity facilitated by PKH social assistants who have previously carried out P2K2 Education and Training debriefing activities carried out by the training office fostered by the coordination of the sub-district area that has carried out the training. KPM PKH group meetings to provide information, education, and administration related to PKH in accessing education, health, and social welfare services by fulfilling the obligations of the needs of each beneficiary family. The role of social assistants in FDS is to increase the potential development of KPM so that KPM can solve problems individually and carry out tasks in community life (Arfiyani et al., 2020)

The implementation of FDS is carried out in rural and urban areas including Sukagalih Village, Garut Regency, Tarogong Kidul District, starting from 2007 until now. In the implementation of PKH, there is also an update which is a re-categorization and takes into account the position of the participants. Updating is divided into 2, namely transition and graduation. Transition is the position of participants, including requirements, having PKH acceptance standards. Graduation is a condition in which poor families must end PKH participation.

There are several descriptions of KPM PKH problems in Sukagalih Village, Tarogong Kidul District, Garut Regency, the identification of the problems as follows:

First, the program target is not precisely targeted in FDS beneficiary families who do not want the end of the assistance period or graduation, graduation is carried out for a maximum of 5 years and must be immediately replaced or graduated. If the implementation of FDS is considered successful in achieving its goals, then the KPM has the self-awareness to graduate

to accelerate poverty. It can be seen in table 1 that 55% of KPM in Sukagalih Village have received assistance for more than 5 years.

Table 1: Beneficiary Family Year Old

Year	During (Year)	Amount	Percentage
2016	6	160	55.4 %
2017	5	39	13.5 %
2019	3	9	3.1 %
2020	2	61	21.1 %
2021	1	20	6.9 %
Total		289	100 %

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2021

Second, based on the results of interviews with several FDS participants, they stated that they did not understand the materials presented by the facilitator from the FDS module. This shows the low responsiveness of FDS participants and the lack of competence of the facilitators to educate the participants.

Third, in the implementation of FDS so far there has been no serious monitoring. This can be seen from the increasing number of KPM from year to year. The amount of PKH Participants in 2019 (253), 2020 (279), 2021 (289 person).

On the other hand, research on the Family Development Session has been carried out by previous researchers including Hia et al. (2021) which discusses the implementation of FDS in the Pekan Complete Village area, Finish Subdistrict, Langkat Regency, North Sumatra with qualitative methods, Arfiyani (2020) which discusses the FDS strategy and FDS achievements, Annisa et al (2020) which discusses the level of program effectiveness towards independence the beneficiary families of the family hope program, Firdaus & Jayawinangun (2019) which discusses FDS in terms of communication effectiveness, and Nurcahya (2017) who discusses the level of efficiency, effectiveness, and responsiveness of FDS in Kebundalem Lor Klaten Village using quantitative methods. On the other hand, research on the Family Development Session has been carried out by previous researchers including Hia et al. (2021) which discusses the implementation of FDS in the Pekan Complete Village area, Finish Subdistrict, Langkat Regency, North Sumatra with qualitative methods, Arfiyani (2020) which discusses the FDS strategy and FDS achievements, Annisa et al (2020) which discusses the level of program effectiveness towards independence the beneficiary families of the family hope program, Firdaus & Jayawinangun (2019) which discusses FDS in terms of communication effectiveness, and Nurcahya (2017) who discusses the level of efficiency, effectiveness, and responsiveness of FDS in Kebundalem Lor Klaten Village using quantitative methods.

However, from the research that has been done, no one has discussed the effectiveness of the Family Hope Program through Family Development Sessions, especially in Sukagalih Village, Tarogong Kidul District, Garut Regency. So the purpose of this study is to analyze the

effectiveness of the Family Hope Program through Family Development Sessions, especially in Sukagalih Village, Tarogong Kidul District, Garut Regency.

2. METHOD

Characteristics in this study using qualitative research with descriptive methods. Qualitative research is used for conditions in natural conditions of objects (as opposed to experiments) as reviewers in research, researchers collect data, key instruments, conduct qualitative analysis and research success is expected to achieve generalization of benefits.

The descriptive method plays a role in describing the sketch of the object to be studied using the data that has been collected. The data can be in the form of written words and verbal forms that are observed. Furthermore, the following data were generated from interviews, documents, pictures, and notes in the field. Phenomena related to the Family Hope Program through the Family Development Session (FDS) in overcoming poverty with a qualitative approach.

According to the data sources, researchers used primary data sources in the form of observations and interviews. For secondary data sources, namely in the form of information from books, journals and data archives related to the Family Hope Program through the Family Development Session (FDS).

The informants of this research are people who are directly involved in the Family Development Session. The key informants in this study were the Head of Village, Head of Welfare and PKH Facilitator. While the Supporting Informants are representatives of PKH beneficiary families as FDS participants.

In this case, researchers can obtain as much data and information as possible related to research problems, namely regarding the effectiveness of the Family Hope Program through Family Development Sessions in overcoming poverty in Sukagalih Village, Tarogong Kidul District, Garut Regency.

The technical analysis of the data in this research is done by:

- a. Collecting data and information against the Family Development Session based on the results of interviews.
- b. Studying and reviewing data and information about the Family Development Session.
- c. Describe the Family Hope Program through the Family Development Session in overcoming poverty.
- d. Next, the researcher draws conclusions from the results of data analysis and explains the results of the study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In analyzing the data that has been obtained, the researcher uses the theory of effectiveness according to Budiani (2007) which can be seen from 4 elements. The first is the accuracy of the program targets. The accuracy of the program targets is the prefix carried out by the

program implementers to implement programs or activities that include making decisions, discussing with the community about criteria, targeting targets so that the underprivileged community has a response to reject or accept the program being discussed. Second, namely the socialization of the program which is a process of providing clear information to transmission (dissemination of information) and consistency to the community aimed at introductions related to the Family Development Session (FDS). Third, namely the purpose of the program of activities starting with the beginning to monitoring the existing resources, coordination and facilities to achieve the target effectively and efficiently. Fourth, program monitoring is the process of successful program implementation as well as the competencies of PKH facilitators, SOPs and responsibilities. Implementation must run as it should to achieve the goal of overcoming poverty. The results of the analysis of the implementation of the Family Development Session (FDS) can be measured by how effective the program actually is in the Sukagalih Village field.

a. Accuracy of Program Targets

The targeting of the Family Hope Program through the Family Development Session (FDS) has been going well, the beneficiaries must have the criteria set by the Ministry of Social Affairs including (1) Pregnant women, (2) Early childhood, (3) Elementary school children, (4) junior high school children, (5) high school students, (6) elderly and (7) disabled. The program targets very poor households who find it difficult to access health education. The poor in PKH become a priority for assistance, and the community can propose or recommend who is the right person to get assistance. The village apparatus also looks at the DTKS (Social Welfare Integrated Data). All of this can be seen from the agreement, and cooperation between the community and the apparatus village to help recipients of assistance to be right on target.

The results of the researcher's observations show that the implementation of the Family Hope Program through the Family Development Session (FDS) is seen from the right target of the program, this is the criteria for recipients of assistance, so that the target of poor families, PKH becomes a priority, has been running. However, the implementation of FDS not being targeted is a problem, with this the end period of PKH assistance is a maximum of 5 years. The low comprehension of the material or module delivered is a measurement that has an impact on the development of knowledge to changes in behavior. Modules or materials delivered by PKH facilitators help improve access to health, and create family support for children's development and education. FDS also helps reduce stressors in KPM through better financial management and coping with family burdens and reducing poverty.

b. Program socialization

Socialization through Family Development Sessions (FDS) has been going well. Information has been conveyed the form of program socialization is conveyed to the community through the local RT, and RW to gather in the village hall. Submissions were delivered directly, some were through WhatsApp Group media specifically for KPM. In the material delivered directly, FDS notification is first to the group leader then the group leader conveys directly to the participant's door to door to notify the implementation schedule 3 days before the

implementation. Clarity of information is the responsibility of the PKH facilitator. Information is also conveyed from the Ministry of Social Affairs, districts, sub-districts, and urban villages, any information must be directly conveyed, whether it is about PKH or FDS. As with KK update information on KPM, information is directly submitted to KPM and coordinates KK updating so that it runs well. The consistency of information in the FDS is carried out consistently, this can be seen from every month there is material delivery in accordance with the modules that have been determined, the modules are about child care and education, mother and child health, managing finances, good parents, understanding children's behavior, learning for young children. early childhood, success in school, careful borrowing and saving, disability protection, elderly health, starting a business, and taking advantage of bank services, many material sessions were delivered and the latest one was about stunting prevention and treatment.

The results of the researchers' observations, PKH assistants were able to deliver material to KPM with the aim of changing mindsets and attitudes for the better. But there are still many KPM that have not been applied or implemented in daily life. The community has not been able to get out of poverty, and FDS is able to move to improve the KPM economy, but in independent graduation, KPM is very low.

c. Program Objectives

The program objectives through the Family Development Session (FDS) have not been maximized. Very little independence of KPM for the continuation of understanding, and application of FDS. The purpose of FDS is to change KPM's mindset, but KPM's participation is lacking. The achievement of goals also includes human resources, the facts in the field of Sukagalih Village are not lacking, but helping each other between the apparatus and PKH assistants. The coordination that went well with openness with PKH facilitators, for example, scheduling the implementation of the FDS which was held in the village hall communicated with each other. Good facilities are made to support FDS such as speakers, mics, laptops, stationery, and whiteboards.

The results of the researchers' observations, KPM in FDS is only an obligation to gather, not with the application of the material in everyday life. KPM participation is lacking in this case if there are KPMs who have problems with slow disbursement, conflicting times in the implementation of FDS due to work, and other reasons that result in not being present at FDS. PKH facilitators can add resources or involve other stakeholders in delivering material related to health, and education. It is better for KPM to use learning materials to improve a better quality of life.

d. Program Monitoring

Program monitoring through the Family Development Session (FDS) is running but not optimal. A report that is made once a month is only to find out how many KPMs are present to participate in the implementation of the FDS. Participants who were not deeply involved, for example, did a text test that made KPM know how beneficial the FDS implementation was. KPM not only gets the module education delivered but also reflects, jokes while learning.

Problems that often occur in FDS are when KPM has less free time and a place to reach the center of the group meeting (FDS). The solution was taken by mutual agreement on the implementation of FDS in the village hall which was previously at KPM's house. There are many reasons for KPM's free time to work, no one at home to take care of the children, even though it can be in accordance with the existing FDS schedule and can work for the common good. KPM skills in starting small businesses, this is also at least KPM who come out of independence or graduation. The KPM feasibility test only invites debate when it has to be decided on graduation so that monitoring is less than optimal and firm, even though the village apparatus and PKH assistants submitting the KPM expiration period if the center does not approve the distribution of aid will still continue. KPM only thinks that the collection is only an obligation to attend but is not utilized and applied.

The competence of PKH assistants plays an important role, such as experience and implementing FDS training which is carried out by the training office and guided by the regional coordinator. The SOP or workflow for companions in PKH begins with preparation for the initial meeting, conducting the initial meeting, conducting group meetings at KPM homes and implementing FDS, updating data, visiting KPM attendance at health or education facilities to monitoring and evaluation, graduation and intervening KPM in empowerment programs or programs. Other. The responsibility of the PKH facilitator is not only about FDS, but also improving administrative data, PKH due diligence and others.

The results of this study are different from the results of research (Firdaus & Jayawinangun, 2019) that the implementation of Family Development Sessions can be said to be effective, supported by the communication skills of credible companions in their fields. This indicates that the competence of the facilitator is a sufficient factor to determine the success of this FDS program.

Furthermore, there are several factors that the implementation of FDS has not been effective, including KPM still lacking understanding of the modules delivered, KPM participation in FDS free time is lacking, and passive monitoring so that the achievement of goals is not maximized. Involving other stakeholders in FDS as a developmental effort can be used as a solution to increase the independence of beneficiary families for changes in the quality of attitudes and behavior. This agrees with the results of research (Arfiyani, 2020) regarding the need for the involvement of other stakeholders, both educators, health, and economics, to fill FDS activities.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, the effectiveness of the Family Hope Program through the Family Development Session in overcoming poverty in Sukagalih Village, Tarogong Kidul District, Garut Regency has not been effective, as follows:

The accuracy of the program targets through the Family Development Session (FDS) is not yet right. All of this can be seen from the agreement, the cooperation of the community, and the Apparatus village to help the beneficiaries to be right on target, this is in accordance with the criteria for the recipients of assistance, the program targets very poor households who find it difficult to access health to education. The poor in PKH become a priority for assistance, and

the community can propose or recommend who is the right person to get assistance. The Apparatus village also looks at the DTKS (Social Welfare Integrated Data) and the KPM's obligation to participate in the FDS.

Socialization of the program through the Family Development Session (FDS) has been going quite well. PKH facilitators are able to deliver material to KPM to change mindsets and attitudes for the better. But there are still many KPM that have not been applied or implemented in daily life.

The achievement of program objectives through the Family Development Session (FDS) has not been achieved. Especially in the implementation of goals that have not been maximized, the application of KPM in the material is carried out only with the obligation to gather, not with application in everyday life. There is still a lack of understanding, sometimes if PKH is not disbursed, they do not participate in FDS. The community has not been able to get out of poverty, and FDS is able to move to improve the KPM economy, but in independent graduation, KPM is very low.

Program monitoring through the Family Development Session (FDS) has not been maximized. A report that is made once a month is only to find out how many KPMs are present to participate in the implementation of the FDS. For participants who were not deeply involved, for example, through a text test that made KPM know how beneficial the FDS implementation was, KPM only thought for the group that it was only an obligation to attend.

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